

The Evaluation of Carbon Emission from Waste Tires Pyrolysis Based on IPCC: A Case Study in Thailand

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ABSTRACT:

This research investigates the carbon emissions related to different waste tire management practices for processing an annual volume of 67,830 tons of waste tires. It emphasizes significant variations in the sources and amounts of emissions throughout pyrolysis, landfilling, and outdoor burning. Pyrolysis is a technique that transforms waste tires into multiple products. All items include syngas (9%), oil (40%), carbon black (32%), steel wire (13%), and sludge (6%). The process of pyrolysis consumes 1.9 MW of power and produces 9.9 MW of energy per year. This strategy is controlled and generally contributes to reduced CO₂ emissions compared to burning waste outside. The net emissions, considering the advantages of energy consumption as well as material recovery, are estimated to be 0.17 – 0.18 x 10⁵ tons CO₂ eq./yr. Landfilling releases a small amount of CO₂ since decomposition is slow. However, this process presents significant long-term environmental hazards related to the emission of methane, which is a potent greenhouse gas. The estimated emissions of methane are between 0.78 - 0.92 x 10⁵ tons CO₂ eq./yr. On the other hand, when tires are burned outside, a substantial amount of CO₂ is released, that's about 1.69 - 1.86 x 10⁵ tons CO₂ eq./yr. This occurs because the carbon content of tires, which makes up 74 – 76% of their weight, undergoes oxidation during the burning process. Pyrolysis is a more sustainably beneficial approach compared to the others mentioned. It is especially beneficial since it allows for the recovery of energy. On the other hand, outdoor burning generates the maximum amount of CO₂ emissions, and landfilling is concerned about long-term methane emissions.

Keywords: waste tire, pyrolysis, carbon emission, waste technology, waste management.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the global environmental situation is facing numerous challenges, with waste management being a crucial factor. The rapid and exponential rise in the production of waste on a global scale, primarily caused by urbanization, population growth, and shifts in consumption habits, is compelling governments and communities across the world to reconsider their approaches to waste management. Conventional methods of waste disposal, such as burying in landfills and dumping in open areas, continue to be widely used, especially in underdeveloped areas. These practices have a substantial impact on environmental degradation, including the pollution of soil and groundwater, the release of air pollutants through waste incineration, and the emission of greenhouse gases that worsen climate change. Furthermore, the rapid increase in the use of disposable plastics is causing waste management systems to be unable to cope, resulting in substantial environmental contamination, especially in marine ecosystems where plastic waste accumulates.

The global waste management crisis is an urgent environmental issue, as evidenced by the statistic that the world generated 1.3 billion tons of waste annually in 2012 and is expected to increase to 3.4 billion tons by 2050 [1]. An estimated 33 percent of this waste undergoes environmentally harmful management [2]. Particularly in low- and middle-income countries, urbanization, population expansion, and economic development are the primary drivers of the increase in waste generation. Landfilling and other improper waste disposal methods contribute to the emission of greenhouse gases, thereby raising the negative environmental impacts. To deal with this crisis, it is essential to implement sustainable waste management systems that prioritize waste reduction, reuse, recycling, and energy recovery in order to minimize environmental impacts and achieve worldwide sustainable goals [3].

The situation of waste tires presents a significant international challenge because of their non-biodegradable nature and harmful environmental impact. Approximately a billion tires decompose annually, requiring appropriate management [4]. Tires disposed of improperly have the potential to cause serious environmental damage, such as pollution and fire hazards [5]. Recycling and repurposing used tires into alternative fuels and rubberized asphalt is a critical activity. Pyrolysis, a technique that allows the recovery of valuable products and provides a solution to environmental pollution, has emerged as a promising method for treating waste tires [6]. Despite the development achieved with sustainable tire technologies, there are still persistent challenges in sufficiently facing the huge amount of waste tire generated on a global level. This highlights the criticality of more extensive recycling and repurposing initiatives.

Carbon emissions from waste, including tires, have a significant climate change impact. Over the course of a century, methane emissions from landfills due to organic waste decomposition are up to 28 times more potent greenhouse gases than carbon dioxide [7]. The central issues pertaining to waste tires revolve around the emission of carbon dioxide during the incineration process, as well as the indirect emissions stemming from the manufacturing and transportation of new tires. Through the conversion of waste tires into commercially valuable products such as gas, oil, and carbon black, recycling technologies such as pyrolysis provide a promising solution by reducing the carbon footprint and demand for new raw materials associated with tire production. The potential consequences of progress in pyrolysis technology on endeavors to mitigate carbon emissions are substantial, contingent upon the provision of sufficient policy backing, investment, and public awareness regarding these technologies.

To overcome these waste management challenges, a comprehensive strategy is needed that combines technological advancements, regulatory structures, and public outreach initiatives. Advanced recycling technologies, waste-to-energy plants, and sustainable product design are increasingly being adopted to minimize the environmental impact of waste disposal and foster a circular economy. For example, nations are progressively implementing policies that require recycling and waste segregation at the point of origin to improve the effectiveness of waste management and decrease levels of contamination. Globally, there is an increasing focus on extended producer responsibility (EPR) programs, which require manufacturers to take responsibility for the environmental effects of their products from production to disposal. These initiatives are

essential for reducing the negative impact of waste on the environment and for guiding global waste management practices towards more sustainable and eco-friendly methods.

The problem of waste, specifically waste tires, poses a substantial environmental issue on a global scale, as well as in Thailand. These challenges are complex, encompassing environmental, health, and economic aspects. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of the extent of the problem, its consequences, and investigating possible solutions, such as pyrolysis recycling technologies, is essential for reducing its effects. Globally, as of 2022, around 1.5 billion tires are discarded each year worldwide. Only in the United States, approximately 300 million tires reach the end of their useful life each year. European countries collectively generate a significant amount as well, and emerging economies like China and India are adding to the numbers at an alarming rate [8].

There are several significant environmental risks associated with improper tire disposal. Waste tires are non-biodegradable and have a long-lasting presence in the environment [9]. Tires that are not disposed of properly can pollute the soil with high levels of toxic metals like lead, zinc, and mercury, which go beyond the acceptable thresholds [5]. These pollutants can have adverse impacts on the environment and potentially impair plant growth [16]. Waste tires exacerbate the issue of accumulating large quantities of tires, occupying valuable space in landfills, and creating habitats for mosquitoes and rodents [10]. Tire fires pose a significant threat due to the emission of noxious gases and oils, resulting in extensive environmental repercussions [11]. Disposing of waste tires in marine environments can cause ecological consequences, as they have the potential to ensnare and injure marine organisms, thereby disrupting coastal ecosystems. In general, the improper disposal of waste tires presents dangers to the soil, air, water, and marine ecosystems, underscoring the necessity for effective waste management strategies.

Thailand is a major player in the worldwide tire and rubber sectors, mostly because it is one of the world's top producers of natural rubber. This availability of natural rubber has not only established Thailand as a significant player in the worldwide market, but it has also fueled the growth of the country's tire manufacturing sector. The favorable climatic conditions for rubber cultivation facilitate large-scale rubber production, the majority of which is shipped to global markets where it plays a vital role in the manufacturing of tires and other rubber goods. Thailand's tire business is flourishing due to its exports, which play a vital role in the country's economy by catering to major automobile markets globally. Report by The Observatory of Economic Complexity, Thailand's rubber tire exports were notably robust, reaching around \$7.2 billion in 2022. The United States emerged as a significant market for these exports, reflecting the strong international demand for Thai-manufactured rubber tires. Thailand's role in the automotive industry has led to a significant increase in discarded tires due to urbanization and economic growth. The lack of adequate recycling infrastructure and advanced technologies exacerbates the problem. Mismanaged waste tires in Thailand pose various environmental and health risks, including fire hazards, water and soil contamination, and the creation of breeding sites for disease-carrying mosquitoes [12, 13]. The situation in Thailand reflects the global challenge of waste tire management, but specific local factors worsen the issue. To effectively handle the magnitude of waste tire production, there is a need for improved recycling infrastructure and advanced technologies [14]. The implications of mismanaged waste tires on the environment and human health are like the global scale, with fire hazards, water and soil contamination, and disease-carrying mosquitoes being major concerns [15].

Efforts focused on addressing the issue of waste tires have resulted in the creation of different recycling and recovery methods, with tire pyrolysis emerging as a highly promising technology. Pyrolysis is a process that entails the decomposition of tires through the application of heat in an environment devoid of oxygen. This transformation results in the production of oil, gas, and char. These secondary products can be used in different ways: the oil can be used as a fuel or as a raw material for making chemicals, the gas can be used to generate energy, and the char can be used as a substitute for carbon black or as a material for making aggregates. This process not only aids in decreasing the amount of waste but also contributes to the production of value-added goods, thus offering a sustainable alternative to landfilling or incineration.

The practice of pyrolysis of waste tires is gaining popularity all over the world as a sustainable method for controlling the growing problem of tire waste. Several countries are leading the way in

the acceptance of this practice and the development of innovative technological solutions. In the USA, companies are concentrating their efforts on improving pyrolysis technology to increase the recovery of oil, carbon black, and steel. Their goal is to develop a circular economy model in the recycling of tires. Pyrolysis is being included into Germany's complete waste management systems, with the goal of maximizing efficiency and reducing emissions. Germany is in the forefront of environmental engineering, and it is a leader in the field. To reduce the amount of waste tires that are sent to landfills and to produce useful by-products such as alternative fuels and construction materials, China has made substantial investments in pyrolysis technology. This is because China deals with one of the greatest quantities of waste tires in the world. In addition to addressing waste management, these advances reflect a larger worldwide shift toward technologies that not only help to resource recovery and environmental sustainability but also address waste management.

Although pyrolysis and other tire recycling technologies have the potential to offer significant benefits, their widespread implementation is hindered by various obstacles. The implementation of these technologies is influenced by regional variations in economic viability, technological challenges, and regulatory frameworks. Moreover, the market for recycled products frequently lacks stability, and the quality of the resulting products can fluctuate, potentially dissuading prospective buyers and investors. To address these difficulties, it is imperative for governments and industries to work together to establish more stringent regulatory norms, encourage the creation of recycling infrastructure, and support research aimed at enhancing the efficiency and quality of recycling procedures. Moreover, promoting public consciousness regarding the significance of appropriate tire disposal and the advantages of recycling can have a pivotal impact on bolstering the circular economy for tires. This paper uses the IPCC method to evaluation the carbon emission caused by tire waste in Thailand through pyrolysis giving insights into the multidimension layout of municipal solid waste management (MSW) in Thailand.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study area was chosen based on the locations of existing tire recycling activities in Thailand. The interview was made to collect data on used of tires and waste tires pyrolysis. Tire recycling processes, waste tires input, pyrolysis products output, and these data was used to prepare an analysis. The study site is in the central of country, where is in Samutprakarn province.

Carbon Emissions Calculation and Analysis

Performing calculations and conducting analysis of carbon emissions in accordance with the guidelines set by the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) is an essential and vital process in comprehending and addressing the effects of climate change. The IPCC offers extensive methodologies that are widely utilized worldwide for the inventory and evaluation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

Annual Tire Replacement (RC) and Waste Tire Generation (WT)

Calculate based on annual car reiterations and tire selling in the country.

$$RC = \frac{\text{Amount of tire sale (ton)}}{V} \quad (1)$$

$$WT = RC \times V \quad (2)$$

Where:

RC = Replacement rate per year

WT = Total amount of waste tire generation

V = Annual amount of vehicle registration

The weights provided are estimated and may differ depending on the manufacturer, tire model, and specific design characteristics such as tread type, steel belting, and tire size, as seen in Table 1. Weights of specialized tires, such as those designed for high-performance sports cars, agricultural equipment, or industrial machinery, can vary significantly from the average weights [17].

Table 1. Average Weight of Tire

Type of Tire	Weight of tire (kg/tire)	Weight of tire (Ton/tire)
Passenger Car	14	0.0154
Van & Pick Up	14	0.0154
Motorcycle	3.4	0.0037
Truck and Bus	50	0.0551

Calculation of Carbon Emissions

The IPCC guidelines establish a methodical framework for the computation of carbon emissions in multiple sectors. The methodologies for national greenhouse gas inventories are covered by these guidelines, which include Energy, Industrial Processes and Product Use, Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use, and Waste [18,19]. General Guidance and Reporting are also included. Their target is to create software and methodologies that are universally accepted for the purpose of calculating and reporting greenhouse gas emissions at the national level. The data will promote the adoption of these tools by all countries that are parties to the IPCC and the UNFCCC [19]. Furthermore, the guidelines provide voluntary industry standards, such as the API Compendium, which aid in the estimation of emissions originating from petroleum industry activities. This ensures that greenhouse gas inventories are dependable, efficient, and comparable [20]. The adherence to these principles is vital for bolstering the precision and comprehensiveness of carbon emission computations, thereby facilitating worldwide undertakings to mitigate and adapt to climate change.

Calculation of carbon emissions from waste tires can be done using the IPCC 2006 guidelines [21]. These guidelines provide a method for estimating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, including carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, from various sources, including waste management processes. The IPCC 2006 guidelines were applied in a study comparing the GHG emissions from different waste management systems, such as landfilling, open burning, and pyrolysis [22].

Landfill

In calculating carbon emissions from wasted tires in landfills, the main gas of concern appears methane (CH₄) according to the IPCC recommendations. This happens because methane is produced via the anaerobic degradation of organic components often present in tires in landfills. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are also significant equation (3-4). However, they usually generate quite a smaller portion compared to non-biodegradable tire materials [23].

$$\text{Emission (CO}_2\text{e)} = \text{DDOC} \times F \times \left(\frac{16}{12}\right) \times \text{GWP of Methane} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{DDOC} = \text{WT} \times \text{DOC} \times \text{DOC}_f \times \text{MCF} \quad (4)$$

Where:

WT = amount of waste tires (ton)

DOC = degradable organic carbon [7]

DOC_f = fraction of DOC that can decompose [7]

MCF = methane correction factor [24]

DDOC = the mass of decomposable DOC deposited

F = the fraction of CH₄ in generated Landfill gas [7]

16/12 = molecular weight ratio between methane and carbon (ratio)

GWP of Methane = 28 over a 100-year period, according to the latest IPCC [7].

Open Burning

To calculate CO₂ emissions from the open burning of waste tires in Thailand, one must have knowledge about the number of tires burnt and the emission parameters linked to the combustion of tire-derived products. The act of burning tires not only generates carbon dioxide (CO₂) but also generates other hazardous pollutants such as sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). The emissions have a significant impact on the atmosphere, leading to air pollution and creating dangers to wellness

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ emission (CO}_2 \text{. eq)} = \text{WT} \times \text{Carbon Content} \times \left(\frac{44}{12}\right) \quad (5)$$

Where:

WT = amount of waste tires (ton) Carbon content is tires consist of approximately 74-76% carbon by weight.

44/12 = conversion factor of C to CO₂

Pyrolysis

In accordance with the recommendations provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), it is possible to determine the total carbon emissions that are produced by a process such as the pyrolysis of waste tires by considering both the direct and indirect emissions that relate to the process. TE, which stands for total carbon emissions, may be stated as the following formula:

$$\text{TE(CO}_2\text{e)} = \text{DE} + \text{IE} - \text{ER} \quad (6)$$

Where:

TE = total emission

DE = direct emission from the process itself

IE = indirect emission, primarily from energy consumption (electricity, fuels) associated with the process

ER = denotes Emission Reductions, which include credits for energy recovery, material substitution, and any other emissions avoided by the process or its by-product

Data Collection

The calculation of carbon emissions was carried out by gathering and evaluating data from both primary and secondary sources. The table contains all the necessary information for conducting an analysis.

The main objective is quantitatively evaluated and compare carbon emissions from waste tire pyrolysis with alternative methods of disposal such as outdoor burning and landfilling in Thailand using IPCC methodologies.

- To Calculate the total carbon emissions from pyrolyzing waste tires from pyrolysis process in the sample site by using the IPCC's standardized methodologies for greenhouse gas inventory.

- To compare the carbon emissions produced by pyrolysis to those of alternative tire disposal methods such as outdoor burning and landfilling, the comparative effectiveness of pyrolysis in mitigating carbon emissions can be assessed.
- To investigate current situation of waste tires management in Thailand. To understand the environmental and climatic impacts of utilizing tire pyrolysis as a primary waste management approach in Thailand.

Table 2. The Necessary Information for Conducting an Analysis

No.	Description	Unit	Source of information
Input factor			
1	The amount of tires input	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant
2	The amount of operating hour	hour/year	Pyrolysis Plant
3	The amount of planned shutdown	hour/year	Pyrolysis Plant
4	The amount of unplanned shutdown	hour/year	Pyrolysis Plant
5	Power installed capacity	MW	Pyrolysis Plant
6	Power consumes capacity	MW	Pyrolysis Plant
7	Power sale capacity	MW	Pyrolysis Plant
Output factor			
8	Carbon Black	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant
9	Steel wire	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant
10	Pyrolysis oil	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant
11	Pyrolysis gas	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant
12	Heavy oil	Ton/year	Pyrolysis Plant

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Waste tire Generation in Thailand

According to the Department of Land Transport's statistics, the number of vehicles in Thailand has increased from 40,712,048 in 2019 to 44,363,975 in 2023, or around 9%. In 2019, 2022, and 2023, more than 3 million vehicles were registered, but the number of registered vehicles was lower than 3 million in 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID-19 breakdown, which affected the country's economic slowdown.

Figure 1. Vehicle Registration between 2019-2023

Evaluating waste tire generated by using the data from 2019-2023 based on lifetime replacement. The tire in each vehicle requires them to be replaced, which usually makes it difficult to predict their lifetime. The mileage for vehicles typically varies between 50,000 and 60,000 kilometers, however this may be influenced by several circumstances. In the transportation sector like bus and truck,

typically the duration for a set of tires is about 6 months. Those tires were retreaded and reused them for roughly 3 months. Thus, the resulting in an average lifespan is around 9 months per set of tires. There are 6 to 10 tires in every set. Annually, the total number of waste tires is estimated to be about 10, with the large tires weighing an average of 50 kg per tire. This amounts to around 310,000 tons per year. Typically, passenger cars replace their tires after 2.5 years of use, leaving about 4,000,000 tires in this category each year, with an average weight of 14 kilograms per tire. The result of calculating the total weight is approximately 240,000 tons annually. The total amount of old tires thrown in will be at least 550,000 tons per year.

Evaluating based on the volume of tire sales in Table 8. Between 2021 and 2023, we sold a total of 165,409,929 tires, of which 66,595,556 were for passenger cars and 14,732,317 were for large vehicles like trucks and buses. Since the quantity of waste tire creation was recommended in terms of mass (tons). Therefore, we converted the totals of tire manufacturing, tire import, and tire export from several tires per year to metric tons per year by multiplying by the average weight of a tire in each category. Table 4.3 displays the tire's mean weight and details of the parameter calculations, while Figure 4.2 displays the result. Based on the total number of used large-weight tires, over 94% encountered some kind of treatment. Reclaimed or crumb rubber factories receive 88% of these tires, whereas pyrolysis plants receive the remaining 6%. The passenger car sector produced approximately 76,800 metric tons of waste tires annually. And pyrolysis is the technique that is utilized for treating about 58% of the total waste tire generated, which amounts to 44,497 tons per year [28].

Table 3. Total Amount of Waste tire Generation between 2021-2023

Type of tire Unit (Million)	2021		2022		2023	
	Tire	Ton	Tire	Ton	Tire	Ton
Passenger Car	22.51	0.35	22.25	0.34	21.84	0.34
Van & Pick Up	7.39	0.11	5.91	0.09	5.27	0.08
Motorcycle	22.37	0.08	21.12	0.08	20.61	0.08
Tractor	0.54	0.03	0.46	0.03	0.40	0.02
Truck and Bus	5.38	0.30	4.97	0.27	4.38	0.24

Waste tire Management in Thailand

The waste tire cycle in Thailand is a thorough examination that encompasses all stages of the tire lifespan, including manufacturing, disposal, and reuse. In Thailand, the primary methods for recycling and reusing discarded tires include heat utilization, tire reclamation, tire-derived aggregate, and direct consumption. Direct consumption is an essential method as well. The research conducted by the Pollution Control Department categorized waste tire management into four categories: reuse, recycling, use as fuel, or unknown disposal. A tiny fraction of non-functional tires is openly thrown in urban area of Thailand or disposed of in landfills.

In Thailand, the most common methods of managing waste tires are pyrolysis (30.23%), co-incineration in cement kilns (17.33%), and rubber reclamation (4.16%) [25]. Currently, waste tires are not used as a replacement for conventional fuel in cement kilns. The pyrolysis process utilizes a horizontal rotating batch reactor to thermally breakdown waste tires, generating three valuable fractions: gas (pyrolysis gas), liquid (pyrolysis oil), and solid residue (carbon black and steel). Devulcanization, or rubber reclamation, is the process of breaking the sulfur crosslinking bond in used tires to create recovered rubber that can be reused. Four types of materials were manufactured, consisting of reclaimed rubber, crumb rubber, fiber, and steel [26].

Thailand is actively addressing waste management challenges, particularly in plastic and fluorescent lamp recycling, aiming to reduce environmental impacts and enhance sustainability. The country is exploring various waste management models, including community-based and municipality-based systems, to efficiently handle plastic packaging waste and promote circularity. Initiatives like banning single-use plastic bags in major retail stores have shown effectiveness in reducing plastic consumption and encouraging pro-environmental behaviors among residents [27]. Moreover, efforts to improve the recycling process of spent fluorescent lamps involve environmental life cycle

assessments and social impact assessments, highlighting the importance of institutional capacity and sustainable financing schemes for successful recycling endeavors. By leveraging these insights and incorporating strategies like retreading, material recycling, and thermal utilization, Thailand can further enhance its waste tire management practices and energy recovery efforts.

However, Thailand's waste tire management has challenges due to lacking recycling infrastructure and regulation gaps, which limit modern technologies such as pyrolysis. Investments in recycling facilities and changes to the law are urgently needed to improve the economic viability and environmental impacts of waste tire management. It is essential to make significant efforts to overcome these difficulties to reduce the environmental and public health hazards caused by the growing amount of waste tires worldwide. The research on intelligent tire waste management underscores the complexities of social and environmental sustainability decision-making, placing particular emphasis on the necessity to identify pragmatic, economical, and environmentally conscious approaches to waste tire management. Furthermore, studies on campaigns to outlaw plastic bags in Thailand highlight how successful these campaigns are at cutting down on the use of plastic bags, highlighting the need of legislative changes in waste management.

Investigate Waste Tires Pyrolysis Process in Pyrolysis Plant

The sample factory is a technological startup that aims to become an established key player in closing the circular economy loop through collaborative partnerships. Their mission is to solve the waste tire problem through their technological know-hows and capture the value typically leaked from industrial waste like old tires. They have been operating since 2014, with over 15,000 tones of end-of-life tires recycled annually. The company prioritizes renewable energy sources and develops new utilization, continuously developing and collaborating with different players in the value chain to increase quality and maximize product use. They create a comprehensive and sustainable waste recycling model with environment-friendly technology and are a leading player in the circular economy framework. The factory has a 12,500 sq.m. facility with 4 pyrolysis reactors, 15,000 tones of tires, recycled capacities, a solar panel 150 KVA, remote control, and SCADA system. The company uses Passenger Car Radial (PCR) as raw materials, which are crushed into small pieces for the pyrolysis process. The waste tire pyrolysis process is controlled by PCR tires and packaged in a flow diagram. The company has a unique pyrolysis process that recycles disused waste tires into useful industrial raw material. The rCB660 wire steel oil is used in various industries, including tires, rubber, plastic, and paint industries. The company also has a new unique technology to improve the quality of existing products, such as rCB330 (hard grade carbon), which can be used as a substitute for virgin carbon black (soft grade).

The company cooperates with major energy power companies to encourage waste management industrially by using waste tires through the pyrolysis process effectively. They operate 24 hours a day and aim to increase their consumption to around 4,000 tons of waste per month in the future and aims to become a key technological player in closing the circular economy loop through collaborative partnerships and focusing on sustainability and safety. Through the analysis of factory data and interviews with factory personnel, it was discovered that this pyrolysis plant was organized into 3 distinct stages.

Operational Management and Pre-Processing

The pyrolysis plant's operational management begins with the systematic reception of waste tires. This is the first step in the process. The establishment of a robust supply chain mechanism that guarantees a consistent and sustainable supply of waste tires is required for this purpose. This mechanism must consider the environmental impacts as well as the logistics costs that are associated with the collection and transportation of vehicles that contain tires. It is necessary to inspect and categorize waste tires according to their size and condition as soon as they are delivered. This preliminary sorting is essential because it influences the efficiency of the subsequent shredding process, which involves reducing the size of the tires to smaller sizes to facilitate the distribution of heat in a uniform manner during the thermolysis process. To avoid introducing non-tire materials into the pyrolysis reactor, it is of the utmost importance that the plant adheres to stringent quality control measures. This is because the introduction of such materials could potentially have an impact on the quality of the pyrolysis oil and gas that is produced, as well as pose potential safety risks.

Furthermore, it is recommended that inventory management systems be implemented to monitor the flow of materials throughout the plant. This will optimize the operation of the plant and reduce the amount of waste produced.

The Management of the Pyrolysis Process

The pyrolysis process, in which shredded waste tires are allowed to complete thermal decomposition in an atmosphere absent of oxygen, is the most important aspect of the plant's operation. For operators to effectively manage this process, sophisticated control systems are required to monitor and adjust temperature, pressure, and feed rates in real time. This is done to maximize the amount of pyrolysis oil, gas, and carbon black that are produced from the material that is tires. The operational parameters of the pyrolysis process have a significant impact on the quality of these byproducts, suggesting that a high degree of precision and control is required to achieve the desired results. To guarantee the environmental sustainability of the process, it is necessary to carefully manage and treat the emissions that are produced by the plant to conform to both local and international environmental standards. The treatment of solid residues, such as steel wires and carbon black, as well as the cleaning of pyrolysis gases prior to their release or use as a fuel within the plant, are both included in this process.

Post-Process Management and Sustainability Considerations

After the pyrolysis process is complete, the focus of management shifts to the management of by products and the marketing of those products. Pyrolysis oil can be further refined into fuels or used as a chemical feedstock. Carbon black can be processed for use in a variety of industrial applications. The formation of partnerships with industries that can make use of these byproducts is necessary to develop a business model that is sustainable. In addition, the plant is required to implement practices of continuous improvement, which involve the routine evaluation and enhancement of its procedures, apparatus, and safety protocols. This is done with the goals of enhancing productivity, lowering emissions, and guaranteeing the safety of its employees. Following up with the latest developments in pyrolysis technology and environmental regulations is a necessary step in this direction. Additionally, it is essential to cultivate a culture of innovation and environmental stewardship among the workforces. In the end, the successful management of a pyrolysis plant necessitates a holistic approach that strikes a balance between operational efficiency, environmental responsibility, and safety. This approach paves the way for a more sustainable approach to the recycling of tires and the reduction of carbon emissions.

Summary of Carbon Emission

To evaluating the carbon emissions of various waste tire management methods for processing an annual amount of 67,830 tons of waste tires, there would be substantial variations in the primary sources of emissions and their estimated values for pyrolysis, landfilling, and outdoor burning.

Pyrolysis transforms waste tires into different components such as syngas (9%), oil (40%), carbon black (32%), steel wire (13%), and sludge (6%). The process utilizes 1.9 MW of power and generates 9.9 MW of electricity on a yearly basis. Pyrolysis is a regulated procedure that typically leads to reduced carbon emissions in comparison to open-air combustion. The net carbon emissions are 17.93 – 18.43 kt CO₂ eq./yr., considering the recovery of energy and materials.

Waste tires disposed in landfills release minimal amounts of CO₂ as they undergo slow decomposition. Nevertheless, they can emit methane, which is a highly potent greenhouse gas, over an extended duration. The immediate carbon equivalent emissions from landfills would be negligible, but they could have a significant and lasting environmental impact over time. Under calculation, the CH₄ emission (tCO₂ eq./yr.) was generated 78.87 – 92.43 kt CO₂ eq./yr.

The process of outdoor burning tires results in the emission of a substantial quantity of carbon dioxide (CO₂) due to the oxidation of the carbon present in the tires. Given a carbon black, comprising 74 - 76% by weight of carbon content under complete combustion, the outdoor burning of 67,830 tons of tires has the potential to generate 184.05 -189.02 kt CO₂ eq./yr., considering the molecular weight ratio of CO₂ to carbon (44/16).

Pyrolysis offers a potentially more environmentally friendly option for handling waste tires, particularly when considering the recovery of energy. Outdoor burning produces the greatest amount of Carbon emissions, while landfilling raises concerns about long-term methane emissions.

Table 4. Compare Carbon Emission from Waste Tire Treatment

Management Method	Key Emission Sources	Carbon emissions (kt CO2 eq./yr.)
Pyrolysis	Carbon content, electricity usage	17.93 – 18.43
Landfilling	Long-term methane release	78.87 – 92.43
Outdoor Burning	Complete combustion of carbon	184.05 - 186.02

Pyrolysis of waste tires offers a sustainable solution to reduce environmental impact. It transforms tires into valuable products like carbon black and oil, decreasing landfill waste and pollution from incineration. The process also lessens reliance on primary resources, promoting resource conservation. Utilizing syngas for pyrolysis creates a self-sufficient system, enhancing ecological benefits. The sale of pyrolysis by-products generates income, offsetting plant costs. Technological advancements improve yield and product quality, enhancing competitiveness in the market. Overall, waste tire pyrolysis shows significant potential in converting a challenging waste stream into valuable commodities while offering environmental and economic benefits.

The market prices for items obtained from waste tire pyrolysis fluctuate based on the product and prevailing market conditions. According to current research, pyrolysis oil, which is produced from waste tire pyrolysis, has experienced an increasing demand in the market because of its potential as a renewable substitute for fossil fuels. According to a reliable source, the pyrolysis oil industry is likely to experience substantial growth. The market size is projected to climb from USD 0.52 billion in 2024 to USD 1.28 billion by 2029, showing a strong demand and a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 19.71% [29].

Furthermore, ICIS has introduced Pyrolysis Oil Pricing Indexes to enhance transparency and facilitate stakeholders' comprehension of price patterns in this developing industry. This project demonstrates the growing consumer and investor demand for chemical recycling outputs, such as pyrolysis oil. Pyrolysis oil serves as a direct substitute for naphtha in plastic production. These advancements indicate that the economic prospects for waste tire pyrolysis products are favorable, with increasing market prospects and more defined price systems to facilitate trade and investment choices.

The market for waste tire pyrolysis products in Thailand is part of the larger Asia Pacific region, which is experiencing significant growth due to escalating environmental concerns and a shift towards sustainable practices. RCB from this sample site can be used in place of N660 carbon black, price is 20 THB/kg. Pyrolysis oil will be sold to the market as bunker oil C. The oil price has the highest volatility, is 15 THB/kg, and steel is 5 THB/kg. Price of steel wires depend on the market. However, they remain on the lower side compared to other products.

Renewable energy solutions can benefit substantially from pyrolysis byproducts. Pyrolysis Oil, also known as Bio-oil, has the potential to be utilized as a fuel in its raw form or can be further processed to produce chemicals or fuels that closely resemble diesel and gasoline. This candidate shows great potential for substituting fossil fuels in a wide range of applications, such as heat generating, power plants, and engines. Syngas, also known as Synthetic Gas, has the potential to be utilized for energy generation either by directly burning it or by converting it into more valuable chemical products or fuels. Due to its high energy content, it can effectively replace natural gas in power generation. The tariff structure for renewable energy obtained from pyrolysis differs throughout countries and is impacted by the overall renewable energy policy implemented. The power selling revenue will be determined based on the tariff set by the Energy Regulatory Commission of Thailand (ERC). The structure of the Industrial Waste Power Plant Tariff will be as follows.

Table 5. Tariff Power Selling Revenue

Capacity (MW)	FIT (THB/kWh)			FIT Premium (THB/kWh) 20 years
	FIT _f	FIT _{v,2020}	FIT	
New VSPP (all capacity)	3.39	2.69	6.08	0.7

In accordance with international initiatives promoting sustainable energy solutions, the conversion of waste tires into usable energy not only aids in the management of tire waste but also powers the production of renewable energy. This technique facilitates the implementation of the circular economy model by transforming waste into valuable energy resources, hence reducing demand for landfills, and decreasing the carbon emissions linked to tire disposal.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of carbon emissions from waste tire pyrolysis in Thailand, within the larger framework of environmental management and technical sustainability, uncovers complex insights essential for policy formulation and execution. The management of discarded tires in Thailand is hindered by the lack of a specialized mechanism for separating them from municipal solid waste (MSW). This segregation is essential because of the unique and intricate composition of tires, which consist of synthetic rubbers, natural rubber, steel wires, and fabric threads, rendering their processing and recycling exceptionally complex. The absence of targeted laws governing the collection, treatment, and recycling of waste tires leads to inefficiencies sustainable management. The enhancement of laws, rules, and regulations might significantly increase the efficiency of waste tire management by formalizing operations such as collecting, storage, and treatment of waste tires. For instance, instituting standardized protocols for source segregation, establishing specialized handling facilities, and creating dedicated recycling factories might guarantee that tires are treated using ecologically sustainable means. The implementation of extended producer responsibility programs, the dissemination of public awareness regarding environmental and health implications, the allocation of resources to recycling infrastructure, and the promotion of research and innovation are essential elements of effective waste tire management.

Pyrolysis may reduce CO₂ emissions better than landfilling or incineration, which harm the environment. Pyrolysis degrades carbon dioxide molecules. Waste tires are decomposed by pyrolysis in an oxygen-free environment. This produces oil, syngas, and carbon black. Given Thailand's focus on energy security and sustainable industry, waste tire pyrolysis provides significant economic benefits. These byproducts have promising commercial prospects: Pyrolysis oil may replace imported fuels, while carbon black is in great demand for making new tires and other rubber-based products, which might boost domestic businesses. Steel wire recycling in the metal business improves resource efficiency, turning environmental challenges into profitable possibilities. These factors reduce industrial waste and increase resource circularity, supporting Thailand's sustainable growth ambitions. Pyrolysis method for used tires in Thailand improves community welfare and environmental health. Pyrolysis removes tires from landfills, decreasing soil and water pollution and large-scale fires. Reduced environmental impact improves community health and living conditions. Pyrolysis facilities also provide consistent jobs and a chance to enhance skills in economically disadvantaged areas. In line with the Thai government's aims of sustainable development and poverty reduction, these social benefits increase public involvement and knowledge in recycling, raising environmental awareness.

This technology aligns with Thailand's comprehensive energy and environmental goals, as outlined in the "Thailand's Alternative Energy Development Plan (AEDP) 2015-2036." This strategic plan emphasizes the expansion of renewable energy sources to mitigate the impacts of climate change. The primary objectives are to reduce carbon emissions and achieve a net-zero emissions profile. The proficient integration of pyrolysis technology into Thailand's waste management system is a strategic action that addresses critical environmental challenges related to used tire disposal while furthering the nation's sustainability goals.

Such technology, regulatory assistance, and public-private partnerships are needed to turn Thailand's waste management system into a circular economy model. Companies investing in pyrolysis technology should get tax discounts, grants, or subsidies from the government to lessen the initial financial burden and encourage market entrance. Tire recycling might be viable by encouraging local markets for pyrolysis byproducts including carbon black, syngas, and recovered oil. Along with legislative and financial incentives, public awareness and education initiatives are essential. These efforts should promote appropriate tire disposal and recycling to encourage a culture of sustainability and recycling. The government, educational institutions, and corporate sector can work together to provide teaching materials and activities that emphasize citizen trash management. Partnering with overseas organizations that have effectively managed discarded tires might bring significant insights and technical skills. This transition will help Thailand meet its climate targets and make it a regional leader in sustainable waste management and renewable energy.

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